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FluidFM Deposition of Semiconductor Quantum Dots From Aqueous Dispersions

Gopinath Manoharan^{1,2} |
Thomas Otto^{1,2,4}

¹Center for Micro and Nano Technologies (ZfM), Chemnitz University of Technology, Chemnitz, Germany | ²Fraunhofer Institute for Electronic Nano Systems (FhI ENAS), Chemnitz, Germany | ³Semiconductor Physics, Chemnitz University of Technology, Chemnitz, Germany | ⁴Research Center for Materials, Architectures and Integration of Nanomembranes (MAIN), Chemnitz University of Technology, Chemnitz, Germany

Correspondence: Thomas Blaudeck (thomas.blaudeck@main.tu-chemnitz.de)

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ABSTRACT

FluidFM deposition, also known as pressure-controlled and force-controlled micropipetting, of nanomaterials suspended in fluidic carrier liquids is known as a capillary-driven, high-precision liquid-in-liquid deposition and manipulation technique in biofluidic environments. In this work, we report on its usage as a liquid-on-solid structuring technique from an aqueous dispersion of colloidal inorganic semiconductor Ag–In–S quantum dots (QDs) stabilized with glutathione ligands on solid substrates. We show the recurrent deposition (3 × 3 matrix) and characterization of three-dimensional liquid-in-air deposits formed by structured sedimentation of the QDs on gold-coated glass substrates upon FluidFM deposition via bottom-up self-assembly. As critical facts for a successful deposition of the QDs turn out: The aqueous nature of the dispersion, the possibility for its careful adjustment regarding density and composition, and an effective surface energy engineering of both the FluidFM cantilever and the gold-coated glass substrates mediated by chemical vapor deposition and physical vapor deposition, respectively. This way, the minimal lateral dimensions of the obtained deposits were (500 ± 40) μm, with evaporation-limited contact-line widths of (2.0 ± 0.5) μm.

1 | Introduction

When deposited locally from a suitable liquid dispersion medium on solid substrates, colloidal nanoparticles can form coherent morphologic entities that enable functional structures with a variety of interesting photonic and optoelectronic properties [1].

Beyond that, such one-, two-, and three-dimensional supras-structures formed by spontaneous intrinsically guided [2] or externally forced self-assembly [3] of nanomaterials can act as model systems for bottom-up microfabrication. In particular, colloidal dielectric nanoparticles—locally deposited on solid substrates and governed by physical or chemical patterning of

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the surface morphology [4] or the surface energy [5]—have proven to form static functional components such as photonic crystals in free-form geometry [6], microscatterers, reflectors, and attenuators [7–12], optical waveguides and interconnects in photonic nanosystems [13–15], electronic wiring [16] or dynamic entities such as micro and nanofluidic channels confining motility of individual functional units [3, 17, 18]. Semiconductor nanoparticles, also known as quantum dots (QDs), have created considerable interest in optoelectronics. They can act as a tunable emissive element in QD light-emitting diodes (QD-LEDs), for which liquid deposition methods such as spin coating, inkjet printing, and micro-contact printing have evolved as techniques for patterned deposition [19–24].

During the last decades, a plethora of deposition techniques for both polymeric materials in carrier liquids and nanomaterial dispersions has been developed. This comprises direct-write and large-area or layer-by-layer techniques. Depending on the continuity of the fluid supply and the deposited material films achieved by the deposition process, direct-write techniques can be roughly classified into classical serial layer-by-layer deposition (stamping) [19], microdispensing from microchannels [13] or capillary tubes [20], “classical” writing with functional inks (zone casting) [25–27], and functional inkjet printing [7, 8, 11, 16, 28]. Large-area techniques comprise complete immersion-based techniques such as modified vertical deposition [29, 30], doctor blading [31], and slot-die coating [32]. All techniques can be employed on plain or prestructured substrates affecting the particular evaporation regimes in response to the local capillary effects.

Scanning-probe techniques based on atomic force microscopy (AFM) have revolutionized the metrology of surface morphology and local properties such as elasticity and charge state with spatial resolutions down to the nanometer range, conditionally, for example, in vertical direction, even down to 100 nm. The introduction of this class of techniques has culminated in solid-state surface analysis with a wide range of applications in air or in vacuo targeting micro and nano electronics [33]. AFM in liquid environments, otherwise referred to as Fluid-AFM, has given rise to measurement methods expanding the scope of AFM techniques to this special case. Employing a combination of the fundamental tapping mode with a secondary, higher-frequency resonance mode, bimodal AFM allows a mapping of high-resolution data on surface properties together with subsurface information. Its ability to detect deeper material features is beneficial for materials science and nanotechnology, especially when the goal is to study mechanical properties beyond just surface topography. Here, the development of bimodal AFM techniques was a key to a mapping of spatial morphology, composition, and physical properties quasi at once and initiated an application boost also for solid–liquid interfaces and soft-matter items such as cells and other biological specimen [34–36].

In contrast to the conventional piezo-controlled excitation of the cantilever in conventional AFM, the BlueDrive technique, developed by Oxford Instruments, employs a laser to directly excite the cantilever resonance, thereby enhancing the overall stability and precision of measurements. It thus offers enhanced stability and sensitivity, leading to improved measurement quality, particularly in liquid environments. In contrast to these Fluid-AFM techniques, which remain pure metrology techniques

in a liquid, FluidFM techniques go some steps further by enabling precise liquid delivery and surface manipulation through the hollow AFM probe. The supply of a fluid environment deposited from the probe to the specimen, on-demand and locally, allows local patterning or the surface, for example, by a deposition or forced adsorption of nanoscopic constituents borne in a carrier liquid onto a substrate. Hence FluidFM techniques allow a gain in versatility of the Fluid-AFM techniques, but require attention to and understanding of the involved basic physical and chemical phenomena at the involved materials and interfaces.

In a pioneering approach, Meister et al. described an AFM setup based on hollow cantilevers for a local dispensing of liquids and a stimulation of single living cells under physiological conditions. [37] Grüter et al. described an AFM setup for nanofluidic deposition. It was equipped with a tubing that connected a perforated AFM cantilever holder to a fluid reservoir, which was subjected to controlled actuation by a pressure controller [38]. They demonstrated a pressure- and force-controlled deposition of fluorescent polystyrene nanoparticles (diameter: 25 nm) capped with carboxylic acid dispersed in ultrapure water on transparent glass substrates. These were coated with a monolayer of positively charged polyethylenimine (PEI) and patterned in horizontal stripes with feature sizes down to 500 nm. The setup involved a perforated AFM cantilever (opening: 300 × 300 nm) acting as nanopipette connected to a microfluidic system, which allowed a precise control of the fluid flow by the pressure (50–200 mPa) and the deposition speed (10–160 μm/s) given by the relative movement of the AFM cantilever with respect to the substrate. The obtained patterns confirmed the possibility of a precise placement and distribution of the nanoparticles on the wetted substrate with a spatial resolution below 1 μm within the patterned stripes. Hence, the proof was conducted that FluidFM deposition of nanometer-sized objects in a liquid environment as a variant of pressure- and force-controlled micro-/nanopipetting can overcome some relevant limitations of traditional lithography methods that often require vacuum conditions or dry environments (“lithography-in-liquid”) [38]. In a similar approach, Ventrici de Souza et al. reported spatially controlled microfluidic dispensing of a commercial adhesive using a FluidFM setup equipped with a nanopipette and a fluidic system [39]. The authors introduce a layer-by-layer deposition method to spot and stack material in a controlled manner, applicable to a variety of materials including metals, polymers, and biomolecules. The liquid materials are deposited layer by layer, that is, wet in wet (“direct delivery”), capable of building up three-dimensional nanostructures including nano-pillars, nano-bridges, in simple and more complex geometries (“three-dimensional nanoprinting”) with a positioning accuracy down to a few 10 nm and the smallest droplet diameter demonstrated down to 600 nm [39]. Further applications of a FluidFM setup were the force-controlled manipulation (injection, extraction including DNA) and mechanical perturbation of single cells at liquid–solid interfaces [40], a template-free 3D microprinting of metals for layer-by-layer electrodeposition [41] studying the interface between a single prokaryote or eukaryote cell and a neighboring surface or surrounding area [42] and generally its utilization for general biomechanical and biophysical issues in life sciences [43]. Further application potential especially in the field of optoelectronics can be anticipated in combining a highly parallelized FluidFM deposition with induced convective

Figure 1 | (a) Sketch of the FluidFM deposition principle (pressure-controlled micro-/nanopipetting) of a fluid onto rigid substrates with or without surface patterning using an AFM setup with a microfluidic control system including specially designed AFM cantilevers for fluidic deposition. (b) Close-up of the cantilever and the micro-/nanopipette. (c) Scanning-electron microscope image (5 kV, magnification 5 \times , SE filter) of a surface-coated micropipette (orifice: 4 μ m) used in this work.

and/or capillary self-assembly processes [44, 45] of dispersions semiconductor QDs from a suitable and easy-to-handle carrier liquid such as water.

With this application potential in mind, in this work, we demonstrate FluidFM deposition in terms of a pressure-controlled, capillary-driven micro-/nanopipetting technique for the deposition of water-soluble, colloidal nanoparticle dispersions to achieve structured functional entities on rigid substrates. We target semiconductor QDs as a potential use case for QD-LEDs, employing a commercial (Nanosurf AG) yet customized fluid-force microscope (FluidFM) with various probes and add-ons, facilitating an exact dosing and positioning of pico- and femtoliter volumes with the local resolution of a regular AFM setup on rigid substrates (i.e., sub-micrometer positioning accuracy). In our FluidFM deposition setup, the carrier liquid is applied via a channel inside a specially prepared AFM cantilever that has a fluidic channel with an orifice pointing in the direction of the solid substrate. The cantilever channel connects to a liquid supply reservoir and a microfluidic pump unit with the help of which the fluid (e.g., nanomaterials stabilized in a carrier liquid) can be dispensed through the cantilever in the direction of the substrate surface by over- or underpressure. In our approach, we concentrate on the understanding of a structured FluidFM deposition process in air as it is known from classical deposition processes such as capillary blading or zone casting and would allow a match with industrial conditions easily. Solving this task is already a research question sufficient complexity. However, the effective transfer of the fluid onto the substrate depends on the involved particular surface energies at the involved three-phase boundaries of fluid and air atmosphere at the AFM cantilever orifice and on the substrate. The primary parameters used to control the volume of applied liquid are liquid pressure and the motion speed of the AFM cantilever with respect to the substrate. The deposition process is further governed by the evaporation process of the eventually transferred droplet. This relates to the fluid composition and the local surface properties of the

substrate. A sketch of the FluidFM deposition principle in terms of pressure-controlled micro-/nanopipetting is shown in Figure 1.

So far, given its origin in biological engineering, commercial FluidFM deposition is optimized for liquid deposition into liquid environments [38, 39, 41]. On the contrary, this work is dedicated to a technical application of this method in the domains of optoelectronics and photonics, which requires a transition to deposition from liquid to solid interfaces such as wafers of silicon, quartz, glass, or other materials. Methods to achieve this goal are a careful engineering of the involved surface energies, for which micro and nanotechnologies offer a wide range of techniques [4, 5]. From this toolbox, we chose chemical vapor deposition (CVD) and local plasma-induced surface modification [46–48] to modify the local surface energy distribution for a control of the order parameter and hence the morphological and functional properties of the obtained deposits.

2 | Materials and Methods

2.1 | Materials

Ag–In–S QD dispersion: Aqueous colloidal dispersions of Ag–In–S QDs stabilized with glutathione (GSH) ligands were synthesized by a protocol adapted from Stroyuk et al. [49]. Briefly, volumes of 0.8 mL of 1.0-M aqueous InCl_3 and 2.0 mL of 0.1-M aqueous AgNO_3 solutions were dissolved in 2.5 mL of deionized (DI) water, 2.4 mL of 0.5-M aqueous GSH solution, and 1.0 mL of 5.0-M NH_4OH . To form QDs, 1.0 mL of 1.0-M aqueous Na_2S solution was rapidly injected into the freshly prepared reaction mixture under magnetic stirring. The obtained QDs were subjected to heat treatment at 96–98 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 10 min. An excess of GSH ligands and by-products were removed by precipitation of QDs with 5 mL of 2-propanol, separation of the precipitate on a centrifuge, and redissolving it in 2.5 mL of DI water under sonication. The resulting QD solution was diluted before deposition with DI water

(1:100, 1:1000, and 1:10 000 dilutions were pretested, and 1:1000 was eventually used here for FluidFM deposition) and mixed by ultrasonication for 1 min. The QD dispersions were filtered by a 0.45- μm syringe mesh filter (PVDF or comparable) and used without further treatments (size selection etc.).

Gold-coated glass substrates: A glass wafer (nominal thickness 500 μm , diameter: 100 mm) was coated with Cr (thickness: 10 nm) as adhesion layer and Au (thickness: 400 nm) by means of standard physical vapor deposition. The wafer was then subjected to standard blade dicing. The resulting chips (dimensions: 20 \times 10 mm) were further pretreated according to the following schemes: (i) via serial immersion, agitating, and flushing in organic solvents (acetone, ethanol, 2-propanol: technical grade), and (ii) via overnight immersion in an aqueous commercial liquid alkaline concentrate optimized for cleaning of glass, quartz, and other optically transparent precision materials (Hellmanex, Hellma GmbH, Müllheim, Germany). Here, the concentration was 0.5 vol%, that is, 1 mL of the concentrate diluted in 200-mL DI water (residual resistance: 18 m Ω ·cm) for 30 min at 70°C. After the procedures (i) or (ii), the chips were flushed and stored in DI water until further use. A set of reference substrates was (iii) left untreated and exposed to normal atmospheric lab conditions until further processing. The pretreatment protocols for the substrates were targeted at both removal of organic impurities and an increase of the polarity of its surfaces. On the basis of AFM mapping, roughness measurements for three different substrate cleaning protocols as pretreatment schemes yielded the following results (in terms residual substrate roughness, RMS): (i) organic solvents technical grade 2.6 nm (\pm 0.3 nm); (ii) Hellmanex alkaline solution 1.2 nm (\pm 0.2 nm); (iii) untreated 1.4 nm (\pm 0.3 nm). Hence, Hellmanex alkaline solution was chosen as the appropriate cleaning protocol as since it provided the better removal of intrinsic organic residues from the gold surface compared to the usual cleaning with acetone and ethanol. Immediately prior to FluidFM deposition, the respective gold-coated glass substrate was purged and dried with nitrogen and treated with an oxygen plasma (PSD Pro Series, NovaScan, Boone, USA) at 25°C (220–240 V, 50–60 Hz) for 180 s, which resulted in a significant decrease of the water contact angle from 58° (\pm 5°) down to 27° (\pm 5°).

2.2 | Methods

Deposition: FluidFM deposition of the aqueous GSH-stabilized Ag–In–S QD dispersions was performed with a FluidFM micropipette using a FlexFPM (Nanosurf AG, Liestal, Switzerland) with FluidFM add-on (Cytosurge AG, Opfikon, Switzerland) on the gold-coated glass substrates in air under ambient lab conditions (precision climatized: temperature 21.5°C, r. H. 50%). The FluidFM micropipettes are tipless cantilevers with an orifice (diameter: 4 μm), mounted at an angle of 11°, and were passivated with SurfaSil by CVD. SurfaSil is a siliconizing fluid used for passivation of surfaces of, for example, chips for polymerase chain reactions (PCRs) [46] or other reaction vessels [47, 48]. It is applied to prevent the vial surface from inhibiting PCR or to reduce sample losses that otherwise would occur due to adhesion to the side walls. Chemically, the chlorosiloxane binds to the surface of the substrate by hydrolyzing the Si–Cl bond to silanol groups, which in turn can bind to hydroxyl

groups [47]. Technically, the FluidFM micropipettes were placed in a reaction chamber consisting of two Petri dishes. Passivation of the micropipette tips was facilitated by addition of 150 μL SurfaSil (Thermo Fisher Scientific) in the smaller Petri dish at 55°C for 15 min. This procedure was followed by CVD saturation of the end groups in a fresh reaction chamber by incubation of methanol (100 μL) for 5 min. Extensive pretests were conducted at the FluidFM setup to study the relevant ranges of idle pressure and contact time between liquid filament and the substrates (“application time”) for a successful deposition of the QDs. Technically, the FluidFM deposition process was carried as follows: At the initiation, the micropipette was approached to the substrate surface with a force of 5.2 nN in contact mode to deposit the liquid filament (proto-“droplet”) from a height of 15 μm above the substrate surface. During the deposition of the Ag–In–S QD dispersion, a pressure of 500 mPa was applied by the microfluidic unit for 500 ms to guide the liquid filament to the substrate. Subsequent to the coalescence of the initial liquid filament with the substrate, a pressure of 500 mbar was sustained as an “idle pressure” and the micropipette was elevated to a height of 10 μm above the substrate surface to facilitate dewetting of the filament from the micropipette and the formation of a sessile droplet on the substrate. Repetition of the process was initiated for a serial deposition of the subsequent individual droplets of the given 3 \times 3 matrix. As a reference technique, manual dispensing of Ag–In–S QD dispersions using a Hamilton syringe (Hamilton AG, Bonaduz, Switzerland) made from boron silicate glass and PTFE (nominal volume for liquid handling 25 μL , precision 5–10 μL) was employed on the gold-coated glass substrates.

Characterization: The topographical characterization was performed with the same AFM setup (Nanosurf AG, Liestal, Switzerland) with tapping-mode cantilevers (with tips) and resonance frequencies between 280 and 350 kHz and 40-N/m force constant (Tap300Al-G). Optical characterization was performed by standard optical microscopy, fluorescence microscopy (Olympus IX51) at various excitation wavelengths (for orientation, not shown here) and photoluminescence (PL) mapping. For the latter, PL spectral maps were recorded using an XploRA Raman microscope (Horiba) at an excitation wavelength of 532 nm, a spectral resolution of 1 nm, and a spatial resolution of 2 μm . Scanning electron microscopy of the used FluidFM micropipettes was performed using a TESCAN GAIA3 SEM-FIB system.

3 | Results and Discussion

The deposition of liquid quantities in the picoliter range requires both high precision and precise knowledge of the involved surface properties of the substrate, of the fluid as well as of the FluidFM micropipette through which the deposition is facilitated. Only for cases in which the affinity of the liquid is greater towards the substrate than towards the FluidFM micropipette, a deposition of the droplet on the substrate can effectively occur. The gold-coated glass samples were carefully cut, cleaned, and adjusted in polarity by PVD plasma treatment as described in the Experimental Section. In the light of the particular polarity of the water-based QD dispersion, the surface energy of the FluidFM micropipettes was experimentally reduced by the CVD silanization with SurfaSil as described in Section 2. The rationale of the passivation was to facilitate a better transfer of the liquid filament from the orifice

of the FluidFM micropipette to the substrate surface. This is an essential step, as the surface tension of the water-based dispersion and the surface energies of the cantilever and the substrate play a significant role in the deposition of the droplet in air. The coating of the outer walls of the micropipette and parts of the inner walls at the outlet results in a hydrophobic character and a reduction of the surface energy and thus wettability. The passivation of the inner walls of the orifice prevents an uncontrolled outflow of the dispersion due to capillary forces without additional application of pressure and the associated evaporation of the water. The passivation of the outside areas of the cantilever and holder leads to reduced capillary forces and counteracts the wettability of these areas [50] by the liquid filament. Altogether, due to the engineered contrast of the involved surface energies, the CVD silanization facilitates a directed transfer of the liquid filament to the plasma-treated, more hydrophilic substrate.

Preliminary tests were conducted using a FluidFM micropipette to determine the parameters for reproducible application of the aqueous QD dispersion. The pressure range utilized for these tests was from 150 to 600 mbar, with an application time of 300 and 500 ms. Furthermore, the idle pressure was varied between 100 and 500 mbar, with the objective of optimizing the stability of the pressure within the channel and to avoid backflow of the dispersion solution between the applications. Based on the results of the preliminary tests, using the silanized FluidFM micropipette, a 3×3 droplet matrix of Ag-In-S QD dispersion was deposited on the substrate in air with an applied pressure of 500 mPa at an application time of 500 ms with the microfluidic unit through the micropipette and a force of 5.2 nN upon contact with the substrate. An idle pressure of 500 mPa was applied between the deposition of the individual drops to prevent an early reflux of the liquid into the fluidic supply system through the cantilever orifice. All individual deposits of the 3×3 matrix were performed under identical environmental conditions at the given experimental accuracy. A microscope image of the resulting deposits in the 3×3 matrix after evaporation is shown in Figure 2a. The deposition sequence of the individual dots is from left to right in lines from top to bottom. After evaporation of the applied carrier liquid and the formation of the deposits, a clear dual coffee-ring effect can be observed on the substrate consisting of an outer and an inner perimeter. The shape of the droplets can be explained by the fact that the used micropipettes are tipless cantilevers with orifice (diameter: $4 \mu\text{m}$), approaching the substrate surface at a tilt angle of 11° . The larger coffee ring occurs directly when the drop is applied to the surface. The applied pressure and imprinting of the cantilever on the surface forces the liquid out of the opening and spreads over the substrate. When the cantilever is retracted after 500 ms, meniscus formation also causes the contact line of the droplet to retract until the resulting meniscus between the cantilever and the substrate is torn off. The dimensions of the largest outer elliptic ring (cf. Figure 2a upper left deposit at position (1,1) in the 3×3 matrix) is $100 \mu\text{m} (\pm 3 \mu\text{m}) \times 142 \mu\text{m} (\pm 4 \mu\text{m})$ and the smallest outer elliptic ring (cf. Figure 2 lower right deposit at position (3,3) in the 3×3 matrix) is $89 \mu\text{m} (\pm 13 \mu\text{m}) \times 101 \mu\text{m} (\pm 25 \mu\text{m})$, respectively. The smallest inner elliptic ring $53 \mu\text{m} (\pm 3 \mu\text{m}) \times 42 \mu\text{m} (\pm 3 \mu\text{m})$ in size. There are two facts observable: (i) a peculiar “dual shape” of the contact line of the deposits and

Figure 2 | (a) Photoluminescence (PL) intensity map of an aqueous Ag-In-S QD dispersion, stabilized in GSH ligands, deposited by FluidFM deposition in air through a tipless cantilever with orifice (diameter: $4 \mu\text{m}$) onto a gold substrate as 3×3 droplet matrix under identical conditions (10 \times objective, excitation at 532 nm, incident power 0.1 mW, spectral detection window 540–720 nm); (b) microscope image of the same 3×3 matrix (10 \times objective); (c) overlay of PL intensity map and microscope image.

Figure 3 | FluidFM deposition of an aqueous Ag–In–S QD dispersion onto a gold substrate as 3×3 droplet matrix (same matrix as shown in Figure 2). (a) Original light-microscope image (10 \times objective) and (b) digitally zoomed close-up, (c) AFM height-mode image and (d) height profile of the inside of a deposit, (e) AFM height-mode image and (f) height profile of the perimeter of a deposit. In the AFM images (10 \times 10- μ m scan range), a two-fold contact line and small particle deposits on the gold surface with a gradient in normal direction to the perimeter are visible.

(ii) the total diameters of the deposits which exceed significantly the opening diameter of the FluidFM probe orifice of 4 μ m. These results can be explained by an initial spreading of the liquid on the plasma-activated hydrophilic surface which is initiated by the application of the idle pressure and the consequent discrete shift (“jump”) of the contact line after removal of the idle pressure initiating a reflux of parts of the fluid volume back into the supply system. The elongated elliptic shape and the head-to-tail configuration of the deposits along the horizontal axis are in accordance with observations from inkjet printing of functional inks loaded with nanoparticles that relate this observation to a lateral coalescence of droplets (also known as “dot touch” from graphical printing). In these phenomena, the dynamics of the contact line formation and the internal fluxes of the carrier liquid within the resulting elongated liquid cap (“bead”) are caused by a preferred evaporation at three-phase boundaries [7, 8, 16, 51, 52], obviously followed by a variation of the slip-stick conditions over one duty cycle for the retracting contact line as described for dual (and multiple) features [53, 54]. In our case of FluidFM deposition, the role of coalescence through “dot touch” can be ascribed to the asymmetry involved in the generation and transfer of the droplet from the FluidFM cantilever to the solid substrate: The shape of the initially generated pendant drop on the FluidFM cantilever depends on the particular position of the orifice with respect to the apex and the symmetry axes of the cantilever (which is not fully symmetric), its transfer to the solid substrate and its evaporation there.

Figure 2a shows a PL map of the 3×3 droplet matrix corresponding to the optical image in Figure 2b, an overlay of both images is shown in Figure 2c. A strong PL response can be detected on the perimeter of each drop, with an asymmetric intensity distribution together with several bright spots present in the inner part. This finding indicates a heterogeneous accumulation of QDs in this area and justifies attempts in literature for a homogeneous accumulation, for example, by adjusting the fluid composition of the carrier liquid [2]. Altogether, the morphology of the obtained deposit resembles typical contact line shape formation principles of deposits investigated for inkjet printing by Perelaer et al. [7] and Soltman and Subramanian [8]. The deposits comprise of an

outer and an inner perimeter presumably resulting from different coalescence encounters of the pendant and sessile drop phases with the substrate surface. In the resulting PL maps, only much weaker signals can be observed on the small coffee ring and the adjacent part of the large coffee ring, indicating a lower QD concentration that is not evident from the optical images. The PL signal inside the droplets was significantly smaller compared to that on the ring, but it should be noted that this region is not completely free of QDs, since characteristic PL spectra were obtained at longer acquisition times. The asymmetric pattern of QDs on one side of the ring can be explained by the orientation of the probe or the airflow inside the AFM setup.

For a more detailed investigation of the surface, topography measurements were performed within the same droplet, exemplified in Figure 3. In addition to the distinct graininess of the surface, which can be attributed to the gold substrate, several small particles distributed on the substrate were observed.

These height maxima can be assigned stacked agglomerations of QDs in the inner part of a deposit (cf. Figure 3c) as well as individual QDs at the immediate perimeter of the deposit (cf. Figure 3e). For the latter, the height profiles in Figure 3f show a height difference of 5 nm, which is twice the average QDs size of 2.5 nm [49]. The finding of a gradually terraced deposition of QDs from the outer to the inner part of the deposit resembles the morphology and preferential orientation of colloidal particles after inkjet printing at the boundary of static contact lines as reported by various groups, especially for evaporative inkjet printing, of different classes of nanomaterials [7, 8, 11, 16, 28].

For comparison, a manual dispensing (Hamilton syringe) of aqueous dispersion of the Ag–In–S QDs was performed at various concentrations. Figure 4a,b shows the PL mapping results of the solid deposits obtained from these significantly larger drops for the 1:100 and 1:1000 dilutions of the stock solution, respectively. The PL signal for the case of dilution 1:10 000 was hardly detectable. The PL intensity of the samples confirms the coffee-ring effect during deposition of the aqueous dispersion of glutathione-capped Ag–In–S QDs on gold surface.

Figure 4 | (a,b) PL mapping results (“Blue maps”) of manually dispensed (Hamilton syringe) aqueous Ag–In–S QD dispersions at two different concentrations. (a) 1:100 diluted stock solution, (b) 1:1000 diluted stock solution.

To validate the deposition of the Ag–In–S QDs, the lineshapes of the PL spectra were analyzed. Figure 5 shows the ensemble PL spectra of the nondiluted Ag–In–S stock dispersion and the PL spectra integrated from PL mapping results of the solid deposits prepared by FluidFM deposition shown in Figure 2, and manual micropipetting shown in Figure 4, respectively.

First of all, the spectral fingerprint of the PL mapping as well as the PL intensity distribution confirm the deposition of Ag–In–S QDs and the well-known coffee-ring effect incurred after the deposition of the liquid film and the evaporation of the carrier liquid [8]. In both dispersion (i.e., stock solution) and as solid films, the QDs dispersed in liquid environments show a broadband photoluminescence with achieved FWHM (full width at half maximum) of 150–200 nm. This result is typical for multinary I–III–VI chalcogenide QDs such as Ag–In–S in solution [49]. The significant PL broadening of the PL of semiconductor QDs can be considered an intrinsic property, explained either by a trapping

Figure 5 | PL spectra for Ag–In–S QDs: (A) from ensemble measurements in colloidal aqueous solution, (B and C) from PL mapping results on deposits after manual dispensing (Hamilton syringe) and spatially integrated from Figure 4a (B: 1:100 diluted stock solution) and Figure 4b (C: 1:1000 diluted stock solution), (D) from PL mapping results on deposits after FluidFM deposition (1:1000 diluted stock solution). In all cases, a clear PL signature of the Ag–In–S QDs is visible, with spectral shifts indicating concentration effects.

of the generated excitons on real defect states, or “self-trapped excitons” in terms of morphological defects, which are caused by a re-arrangement of the crystal lattice during the process of the light absorption. It has to be assumed that the polydispersity of the QDs in the used dispersions also contributes to the broadening of the PL spectra. The PL lineshape of QDs in dispersions and solid films appear similar, but for the solid films, a slight red shift of the PL maxima can be observed. This observation can be attributed to a charge transfer from the QD solid deposit to the gold substrate. The order of magnitude of the red shift appears larger for the more dilute solutions, which goes along with a larger number of QDs in direct or closed interaction with the gold substrate. The two-fold ring structure could be explained as follows: A first ring can be ascribed to flow and sedimentation during initial coalescence, and a second ring with a smaller diameter, which occurs after retraction of the cantilever and an induced contact-line shift in the wake of the evaporation of the sessile droplet. A macroscopic reference measurement by manual pipetting using a microsyringe at different dilution levels confirmed the coffee-ring formation of the dispersion during evaporation, but shows only one ring, contrary to FluidFM micropipetting. A reason for this finding can be ascribed to the differences in the evaporation at macroscopic and microscopic length scales also found for inkjet printing [11, 28] in which the typical interaction distances of the solid constituents along with the local surface energies affect the local wetting behavior and hence their local (i.e., radial) effective deposition.

4 | Summary and Outlook

Our results document that FluidFM deposition—in terms of an automated pressure-controlled micropipetting technique in air—can facilitate a targeted and reproducible deposition of

glutathione-capped Ag–In–S QDs from aqueous diluted colloidal dispersions in the form of a 3×3 array on rigid gold substrates. As expected from other related evaporation-limited fluid deposition techniques on the microscopic length scale, the sessile droplets show a two-fold coffee ring formation. A PL mapping of the deposited films excludes a presence of QD solids between the two coffee rings, but the AFM measurements indicate that QDs are also present in spread manner at low concentrations inside the smaller coffee ring. The PL spectroscopy measurement performed on the macroscopic solid deposits reveals a clear red shift, which grows with increasing dilution indicating the role of the formation of QD solids. As the local kinetics of the QD deposition process is mainly governed by the interaction of the glutathione ligands with its environment, that is, both the carrier liquid and the involved surfaces, our results can be an example for aqueous dispersions of a variety of QD from materials such as Ag–In–Se, (Cu, Ag)–In–S and the well-described, yet toxic CdSe, stabilized by glutathione [55–57]. Endeavors to obtain smaller feature sizes of the QD deposits and more homogeneous QD films could be conceived in the classical approach of FluidFM operating liquid-in-liquid; however, this attempt would require a detailed understanding and a targeted manipulation of the compositions of the respective carrier liquid and the immersion liquid. For our simpler approach in air presented here, understanding on the role of patterned coatings on the solid substrate surface with switchable, for example, biocompatible thermoresponsive polymers, a topic which has gained considerable progress recently [58–60], could be a viable research path. Such tools of molecular engineering of surfaces and interfaces can be helpful to tune deposition parameters such as local dewetting, wetting, and evaporation time, triggering the liquid transfer from the FluidFM cantilever to the substrate and thus exercise a considerable degree of control of the local deposition result.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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